

The LROSE Science Gateway: Accessible Lidar and Radar Processing in the Cloud

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ABSTRACT

Radar and lidar instruments are widely used for the remote sensing of the atmosphere in three dimensions. These are complex instruments that produce copious quantities of data. Both the size of the data, and the complexities associated with real-time applications and post-analyses, pose a challenge for researchers, students, and instrument developers. Good software tools are needed to facilitate research and education and to maximize returns on NSF investments in observing facilities for atmospheric research. The Lidar Radar Open Software Environment (LROSE) [1], funded by NSF and developed collaboratively by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) and Colorado State University, is a tested and documented software toolbox for analyzing radar and lidar data.

Installation is one of the biggest challenges for users of research-grade software. Based on community feedback from prior and recent surveys, LROSE is no exception. The LROSE science gateway was developed as an accessible solution to the installation problem, providing a web-based interface and allowing jobs to be run on NSF-provided resources in the cloud. The gateway will extend these services available to users who otherwise might not be able to install the software on their desktops, laptops, or servers or use only a few applications.

Currently, the gateway supports a few key functionalities. A user can run a subset of key LROSE applications individually. A popular workflow that estimates rainfall from radar data steps a user through a series of applications that convert data into a standard format, calculate key parameters and three-dimensional precipitation rates, and estimate the rainfall occurring just above the surface. Users can upload their own research data, access radar data in tutorials, and grab operational National Weather Service Next-Generation Radar (NEXRAD) directly from the cloud through Amazon Web Services. Future plans include expanding to other data sources in the cloud, implementing other key LROSE workflows, such as the Wind Analysis workflow shown in Figure 1, and developing modules that educators could use in the classroom

to teach students about radar and lidar data processing. The wind analysis tools are a critical piece of LROSE that can be computationally expensive. Workflows for research and educational purposes also support the continued development and improvement of tutorials and documentation for users.

Figure 1: The Wind Analysis Workflow designed by the SCGI UX/UI team.

Keywords—gateway applications; radar; lidar; atmospheric science

REFERENCES

- [1] Michael M. Bell, Michael Dixon, Wen-Chau Lee, Brenda Jarvornik, Jennifer DeHart, and Ting-Yu Cha, 2021: nsf-lrose/lrose-elle: lrose-elle stable final release 20210312. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5523312>.